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D2.4 – BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report

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Lead author	Dick M.A. Schaap (MARIS)
Contributors	Robin Kooyman (MARIS), Peter Thijssen (MARIS), Paul Weerheim (MARIS), Serge vd Horst (MARIS), Tjerk Krijger (MARIS), Marco Alba (ETT), Erwan Bodere (Ifremer), Massimiliano Assante (CNR), Alexandra Kokkinaki (NOC-BODC), Gwenaëlle Moncoiffe (NOC-BODC), WB1 and 2 teams
Peer reviewers	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT), Pasquale Pagano (CNR), Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)
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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure
BEACON	Data Lake solution
CDI	Common Data Index (SeaDataNet)
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CMC INSTAC	Copernicus Marine In Situ Assembly Centre
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web (OGC standard)
DAB	Discovery and Access Broker
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DTO	Digital Twins of the Oceans
ELIXIR-ENA	European Nucleotide Archive (ELIXIR service)
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data network
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERDDAP	Environmental Research Division's Data Access Program
EuroGOOS	European contribution to GOOS program
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

NODC	National Oceanographic Data Centre
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
SeaDataNet	pan-European network for marine and ocean data management
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated <i>Arctic</i> Earth Observing System
SQL	Structured Query Language
TSC	Technical and Scientific Committee
UI	User Interface
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WEkEO	WEkEO is one of the 5 Copernicus DIAS, bringing in the CMEMS, C3S and CAMS
WFS	Web Feature Service (OGC standard)
WMS	Web Map Service (OGC standard)
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service (OGC standard)
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZARR	Effective format to store large N-dimensional data in the cloud and access chunks

Keywords

Blue-Cloud 2026, EOSC, Marine research, Open Science; Data Discovery; Data Federation; Data Access; Subsetting, Data Lakes, Federated Access

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **Blue Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS)** is one of the core components of the Blue-Cloud technical framework. It facilitates the discovery and retrieval of marine data sets and data products from blue data infrastructures (BDIs), such as key EU infrastructures such as EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, and more, for external users in stand-alone mode. It also interacts with the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment, the component federating computing platforms and analytical services, for populating the VRE data pool. As part of the predecessor pilot Blue-Cloud project, the first operational release of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS has been deployed. The current version of the service is federating in total of 8 BDIs and with 9 data services.

As part of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, it is planned to expand and optimise the DD&AS and its FAIRness, among others by developing and deploying data sub-setting and extracting services, in addition to discovery and access, and by building Blue-Cloud Data Lakes for use by Blue-Cloud WorkBenches and beyond. This objective is subject to Task 2.3 which has been underway since the first STC meeting in March 2023 and the results of analysis and planning are now documented in this Report **D2.4 -BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report**.

It is planned to deploy two configurations of data lakes, one for access by all Blue-Cloud VRE users, comprising a series of data lakes for data sets managed by selected Blue Data Infrastructures, engaged in the Blue-Cloud project, and from an international data repository, the World Ocean Database (WOD), managed by NOAA, USA. A second configuration will consist of two data lakes, one for WorkBench 1 (T&S) and one for Workbench 2 (Eutrophication), set up by merging and harmonising a number of data set collections for selected parameters (EOVs) from multiple BDIs. Moreover, it has been decided to undertake this challenge by adopting the new Beacon data lake technology, which Blue-Cloud 2026 partner and technical coordinator MARIS has been developing successfully over the last three years. This Beacon technology provides capabilities for building data lakes with fast subsetting. It allows slicing through millions of NetCDF files to give in an instant a homogeneous output file with values that could be used for further analytics or to drive a viewer to show in a sliding way e.g. temperature in the oceans at selected dates, locations, and depths. Finally, the Deliverable documents the implementation plan with actions, which are partly underway and partly planned in the near future as part of WP2 for establishing the data lake configurations, their deployment at the Blue-Cloud VRE, and their provision to Blue-Cloud VRE users respectively their integration with analytical pipelines as planned for the WorkBenches.

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1. Introduction

The **Blue Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS)** is one of the core components of the Blue-Cloud technical framework. It facilitates the discovery and retrieval of marine data sets and data products from blue data infrastructures (BDIs), such as key EU infrastructures like EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, and more, for external users in stand-alone mode. It interacts with the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment, the component federating computing platforms, and analytical services, for populating the VRE data pool. As part of the predecessor pilot Blue-Cloud project, the first operational release of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS has been deployed. The current version of the service is federating in total 8 BDIs and with 9 data services.

In the framework of the ongoing Blue-Cloud 2026 project, it is planned to expand and optimise the **Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access service (DD&AS)** and its FAIRness by:

1. harmonising and expanding functionality of web services as operated by each BDI for discovery and access of managed data resources, and as used in DD&AS, following FAIRness review
2. expanding the DAB Common Metadata Profile with extra metadata fields
3. developing and deploying semantic brokering as part of DD&AS interface
4. federating additional BDIs into the DD&AS (EMSO, SIOS, EMODnet Physics, ELIXIR-Mgnify)
5. developing and deploying data sub-setting and extracting services, in addition to discovery and access, and for building Blue-Cloud Data Lakes for Blue-Cloud WorkBenches and beyond
6. tuning Data Lakes developments with Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) developments, in particular EDITO-Infra and EDITO-Modellab.

Items 1 to 3 are the subjects of Task 2.1 and have resulted so far in **D2.1 - Existing DD&AS and Blue Data Infrastructures – Review and Specifications for Optimisation Report (October 2023)**, which gives a review and several actions for BDIs and DD&AS core components which are underway.

Item 4 is the subject of Task 2.2 and has resulted so far in **D2.2: New Blue Data Infrastructures – Service Analysis Report (November 2023)**, which gives descriptions of the new to be connected BDIs (EMSO, EMBRC, SIOS, EMODnet Physics), analyses, in particular about how to fit their output in the DD&AS 2-

layer approach and suitability of their existing web services, and actions which are underway for adding the offerings of the new BDIs to the DD&AS.

Item 5 is the subject of Task 2.3 for which the results of analysis, discussions and planning are documented in this Report **D2.4 -BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report**. The T2.3 activity started at the first Technical and Scientific Committee (TSC) meeting, 28-29 March 2023 in Amsterdam – Netherlands, where a brainstorm was held on data lakes, different technical solutions to achieve this, including for the first time a prototype demonstration of Beacon, a new development by MARIS. The STC group indicated great interest in further exploring and deploying on-the-fly sub-setting functionality from the perspective of BDIs and Work Benches, as it would allow to build up and maintain data lakes for specific parameters by extracting regularly from BDI data repositories. Since then, further discussions and activities have taken place, including tuning between WP2 and WP3, leading to more mutual understanding about WorkBench data requirements, further progress with technology developments, and conceptual thinking about data lake configurations. Intermediate progress was discussed at the GA meeting, 8-9 November 2023, in Rome - Italy, while at the recent STC meeting, 5-6 March 2024, in Amsterdam - The Netherlands, conceptual decisions were taken. The one-year-long consultation and prototyping phase has resulted in concrete plans for establishing data subsetting capabilities in the Blue-Cloud ecosystem and implementing that vision by deploying a series of data lakes at the Blue-Cloud VRE for data repositories and data collections in support of VRE users and developers of the WorkBenches. This Deliverable **D2.4 -BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Concept and Specifications Report** will give more details about the envisioned data lake configurations and also about the technology that is being adopted for powering the data lakes. Finally, it will give information about the implementation planning and related actions. These are already ongoing and being worked out as part of WP2 Task 2.3.

2. Data Lakes for subsetting services

The STC meeting in March 2023 indicated great interest in further exploring and deploying sub-setting functionality from the perspective of BDIs and Work Benches. With the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS) users can discover and retrieve multiple data sets. However, these are data files as managed in the data repositories of the Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) that are federated in the DD&AS. Subsetting capability means that it should be possible to slice through those predefined data files, querying for parameters, depth, location, time period, and other criteria, to generate homogeneous result files that contain the selected values and associated metadata, derived from all the predefined data files. The output can then be used for further analytics or to drive a viewer to show in a sliding way e.g. temperature in the oceans at selected dates, locations, and depths. A prerequisite for the subsetting is that it really should perform on millions of data sets as a user in the given example of the viewer would like to browse using sliders for depth, parameters, and dates at a comfortable pace without having to wait. Such a subsetting capability will also allow to building up and maintaining **data lakes** for specific parameters by extracting regularly from BDI data repositories. And at the same time, on-the-fly subsetting would overcome one of the most important hurdles in working in VRE's: Accessing directly a harmonised dataset with only the data needed, in one file. This interest was later also confirmed in the bilateral meetings with the BDIs. Several BDIs are managing large volumes of data sets which include many numerical data and which are provided in formats such as NetCDF, ODV ASCII, and other ASCII formats.

There are already some tools available, like **THREDDS Data Server (TDS)** based on **OPeNDAP**, **ERDDAP**, and others. However, achieving performance when accessing and extracting big multidisciplinary data resources is a major and ever-increasing challenge. This is true already when dealing with one repository; it is even more challenging to extract data from multiple data repositories. In a perfect world, users should be able to retrieve data uniformly from different data infrastructures following their selection criteria, including for example spatial or temporal boundaries, parameter types, depth ranges, and other filters. In the following different options supporting the data lake vision are being described, resulting in a choice of technology for the Blue-Cloud.

2.1. Beacon

Looking at the data subsetting challenge, Blue-Cloud 2026 partner MARIS, since summer 2021, has been developing the **Beacon software system** with a unique indexing system that can, on the fly, extract specific data based on the user's request from millions of observational data files containing multiple parameters in diverse units. The Beacon system and its data can be accessed via a REST API that is exposed by Beacon itself meaning clients can query data via a simple JSON request, which could be integrated in Jupyter notebooks. The system is built in a way that it returns one single harmonised file as output, regardless of whether the input contains many different data types or dimensions. In practice, Beacon can function as

a **data lake** bringing together millions of e.g. NetCDF files from multiple repositories, and after initial indexing (taking several hours), allowing to extraction of subsets and exporting these in one coherent NetCDF file in seconds.

During the Blue-Cloud 2026 meetings, the interest in Beacon not only came from the BDIs, but also from the WP3 team members, who are developing WorkBenches for EOVs, and who are looking at a relatively easy and efficient way to get input of large amounts of data sets for selected parameters from multiple data repositories and preferably already in a homogeneous way considering formats, parameters, units and other core metadata. If that could be arranged by WP2, then the WorkBench teams could focus on the analytical pipeline aspects such as identification and removal of duplicates, quality validation, and aggregation, which should lead to high-quality EOVS data collections as output. For that reason, tuning has taken place between WP2 and WP3, and following convincing Beacon demonstrations the WorkBench teams have become supportive of adopting Beacon technology for arranging the data provision. In the following more information will be given about the Beacon features and also about other big data solutions as practiced and validated by partner Ifremer, which are interesting for the Blue-Cloud developer community. Also, a practical use case will be highlighted where partner ETT as coordinator and central operator of EMODnet Physics successfully tested Beacon technology in comparison to ERDDAP.

Considering the potential of the Beacon software and the great interest during demonstrations, not only in the Blue-Cloud community but also wider such as e.g. the EuroGOOS operational oceanography community, MARIS has accelerated its development. As a result, there is now a mature beta version (see <https://beacon.maris.nl/>), which has been implemented for the full data collections of SeaDataNet CDI (ca 4 million NetCDF files), Argo-EuroArgo (ca 3.5 million data sets), and is being adopted by EMODnet Physics for driving time series plots of individual observation stations. These implementations demonstrate that the BEACON system is very fast and efficient in performance, and easy to deploy as a high-performance data lake and processing platform for access and sub-setting of big environmental data.

2.1.1. Description of Beacon

Beacon is a high-performance data lake designed for subsetting and storing large quantities of climate data. Beacon is written from scratch in Rust and C and makes use of many new OS kernel APIs to enable its high performance.

The goal of this data lake is to provide an easy-to-use, fast, reliable, and scalable solution for storing, processing, and querying large amounts of climate and marine environmental data.

Features of Beacon are:

- **Direct and Powerful Subsetting:** Beacon facilitates on the fly subsetting of millions of datasets and responds within milliseconds. It enables subsetting using the following methods:

- Range (min,max) filtering of every column/parameter
 - Polygon filtering
 - Filtering on metadata
- **Ease of Use:** The data lake provides a simple and intuitive REST API with swagger documentation, making it easy to store, process, and retrieve/query your data.
 - **Cross Platform:** Support for the following platforms:
 - Docker
 - Linux
 - Windows
 - **Understanding Every Data Dimensionality:** Beacon understands how dimensionality in data sets represents the data and thus doesn't require to harmonise or prepare your datasets. Whether the dataset is 1-dimensional or 4-dimensional, Beacon understands it.
 - **Data Harmonisation:** With Beacon users are able to harmonise various parts of your datasets and build even more powerful products. Various parameters can be harmonised together or even converted between different units, all on the fly using Beacon. This can all be done within a Query.
 - **Many Output Formats:** Beacon can create a single harmonised output in many different formats such as:
 - NetCDF
 - Parquet
 - JSON
 - GeoJSON
 - CSV
 - **Performance:** Beacon is designed with performance in mind. Subsetting from millions of observational data records within seconds can enable a new range of applications to be built.
 - **Scalability:** The data lake is designed to be highly scalable, allowing to store and process terabytes of data without sacrificing performance.

Upcoming Features (part of next Beacon version release):

- **Union Queries:** With Beacon, it is possible to run union queries which enables users to run multiple individual queries at once and combine the results of those individual queries into a single aggregated and harmonised result file.
- **Federated Queries:** Using federated queries, it is possible to run a query against another Beacon instance instead of just the one you're running the query against. In combination with union queries, this would allow users to run multiple federated queries against various Beacon instances and produce a single harmonised output file to the user.
- **Dynamic Chunking:** Beacon is able to create chunks of loaded datasets which will allow for even more efficient querying. Beacon makes use of a method called, Relative Optimised Chunking, that chunks datasets based on its actual data contents, instead of the dimensions provided by the dataset. This means observations of a dataset will be chunked into parts that are in close proximity to each other (Eg. in longitude, latitude, time and depth). This allows for more efficient data retrieval, as Beacon can just load in the chunks required instead of the entire data array for a variable (eg. temperature).

2.1.2. Beacon Binary Format

The Beacon Binary Format is designed to deliver high-performance data access and small data size. This format provides efficient storage and retrieval of data using variables and dimensions, accompanied by attributes to store metadata. The Beacon Binary Format draws inspiration from existing formats like NetCDF but introduces improvements to achieve significantly faster performance and support for multiple readers simultaneously.

Many existing formats involve deserialisation costs, which can be a performance bottleneck when dealing with large datasets. Additionally, compression techniques employed in some formats can introduce overhead and hinder data access speed. The Beacon Binary Format addresses these issues by eliminating deserialization costs and using performance focused compression algorithms while ensuring efficient data representation.

The Beacon Binary Format offers several key features that distinguish it from other formats and make it a desirable choice for high-performance data processing:

- **Zero Copy Deserialisation Cost:** The Beacon Binary Format eliminates the need for deserialization, allowing for direct access to data without incurring performance penalties. This advantage is achieved by storing data in a format that is directly compatible with the target language, avoiding the need for conversion or parsing operations during data retrieval. This format is designed to optimise data retrieval and manipulation operations, resulting in improved performance, especially for large-scale datasets.

- **Small Data Size:** The Beacon Binary Format focuses on minimising data size through compression without losing any performance. By utilising a compact binary representation, it achieves reduced storage requirements, facilitating faster data transfer and reducing storage costs.
- **Variables and Dimensions:** The format adopts a flexible structure by employing variables and dimensions to organise and represent data. Variables allow for the storage of multi-dimensional arrays, while dimensions define the size and shape of these arrays. This structure offers versatility and facilitates the storage of complex data structures.
- **Metadata Storage using Attributes:** Metadata plays a crucial role in describing and providing additional context to the stored data. Beacon employs attributes to store metadata, enabling the association of descriptive information, annotations, and other relevant attributes with the variables or on a global level with the dataset. This feature enhances data interpretability and facilitates efficient data management.
- **Simultaneous Multiple Readers:** The Beacon Binary Format supports concurrent access by multiple readers. This capability allows for parallel processing and efficient distribution of computational tasks across multiple threads or systems, contributing to improved performance in scenarios involving high-volume data access.

NetCDF, a popular data format for scientific and geospatial data, shares similarities with the Beacon Binary Format. However, the Beacon Binary Format improves upon NetCDF in several ways:

- **Enhanced Performance:** By eliminating deserialization costs and using performance focused compression algorithms, the Beacon Binary Format achieves higher performance compared to NetCDF. These optimizations reduce data access latency and enable faster computation on the stored data.
- **Concurrent Readers:** Unlike NetCDF, which typically supports a single reader at a time, Beacon Binary Format allows for concurrent access by multiple readers. This feature is particularly advantageous in scenarios where parallel processing and distributed computing are crucial.

2.1.3. Beacon Performance Indications

Beacon offers powerful query capabilities and can filter on ranges, polygons and metadata. To illustrate this a test was done by loading Beacon with an increasing number of NetCDF files for Temperature and Salinity as derived from the SeaDataNet CDI Data Discovery and Access service.

PERFORMANCE

Figure 1 – Performance of Beacon queries for case with increasing number of SeaDataNet NetCDF files loaded into Beacon instance

In total more than 2.5 Million NetCDF files were loaded into Beacon after which queries were performed. For this test, an instance of Beacon was deployed on a relatively small server (8 cores and 32 GB RAM). This implies that even a modern laptop will give even better results, not to speak of fast computer clusters as available in the Blue-Cloud VRE (D4Science e-infrastructure). The following image gives the results of the test queries, which are very good and can be repeated with different queries without any extra effort.

Users are invited to try out Beacon themselves. This can be done using a Beacon instance which has been loaded with several millions of NetCDF files from the EuroArgo - Argo service, which is one of the Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) in Blue-Cloud 2026. The Argo program is an international collaboration that collects high-quality temperature and salinity profiles from the upper 2000m of the ice-free global ocean and currents from intermediate depths. The data collected provides essential information for climate monitoring, for operational oceanography and for ocean and climate research. Argo is a major contributor to the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and to the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS).

The Beacon instance for Argo is made by a Swagger API at: <https://beacon-argo.maris.nl>

Note: It contains all Argo profiles up until November 2023. Developments are ongoing as part of Blue-Cloud 2026 for a Beacon instance with regular incremental updating following new profiles collected by the Argo programme.

Figure 2 – Swagger API of Beacon test instance for EuroArgo – Argo profiles

2.2. Solutions as applied by Ifremer for big data handling and subsetting

Partner Ifremer is dealing a lot with big data challenges and is trying out several solutions. Therefore, it is interesting to summarise their approaches and experiences as this will enlarge the knowledge base of the Blue-Cloud 2026 developers.

2.2.1 In-situ data

Historically, Ifremer used relational databases (e.g. Oracle, MySQL, PostgreSQL) to:

- collect and store data with reference constraints (e.g. data conformity)
- data curation (e.g. quality control)

- data dissemination (e.g. diffusion)

As the volume of data increases and the need to access data grows, this solution reaches its limits, as locks are placed on writes and queries are complex because of the normalised mode (many joins). The solution chosen by Ifremer is to have one model for data management (normalised model) and another for dissemination (denormalise model). With the emergence of big data solutions, Ifremer has configured the following solution:

- Data is exported in a fixed number of Parquet files. These files are used to populate Elasticsearch (for the metadata) and Apache Cassandra (for the data), but are also used to extract a subset of data. Apache Spark is used to parallelise the different processes.
- A web API has been developed to search a platform or a cycle via their metadata (i.e. geospatial, temporal, quality flag) and to retrieve the corresponding measurement. Elasticsearch is a great tool to index metadata and provide full search, spatio-temporal search and aggregation. The result from Elasticsearch facilitates identifying the partition keys in Cassandra for fast and efficient data access. The result can be down sampled on the Cassandra clusters via a Spark process. In this way, the client receives only a small part of data, while maintaining a consistent representation of the data. Data visualisation in the web browser in charts is then very fast.

Summarising:

- Parquet is used for parallel processing
- The combination of Elasticsearch and Cassandra is used for interactive applications

The advantages of such a solution are: scalability (e.g. clusters, parallel computing), efficiency and robustness.

The drawbacks of Elasticsearch and Cassandra can be:

- need for a specific, dedicated infrastructure (clusters)
- need an IT team to maintain these platforms
- requires big data skills in development team
- data storage strategy is tuned for a specific usage

2.2.2 Satellite data

As the volume of satellite data is too huge (> Pio), Ifremer does not use a database to store the data, but stores the files directly on the filesystem. However, there is a need to index files (i.e. data inventory) so that files can be quickly retrieved, and cross-searches, colocation and co-registration can be performed.

Most of the files are now in NetCDF4 format, using HFD5 as backend. This enables Ifremer to use chunks natively. With the emergence of solutions promoted by the Pangeo community (e.g. ARCO formats, intake, Dask), Ifremer generates Zarr emulation files with Kerchunk (<https://guide.cloudnativegeo.org/kerchunk/intro.html>).

This can be tested via: <https://pangeo-forge.org/>.

The advantages of kerchunk:

- avoids duplicating data. It contains only the aggregated metadata that points to chunks in native files
- enables the use of Pangeo solutions (e.g. Xarray, Dask, intake)
- enables fast access to a datacube (performance quite similar to Zarr)
- can be applied on local or remote files (e.g. server over http or s3 protocols)

Some drawbacks of kerchunk:

- does not work on non-homogeneous data series (need to process them independently)
- the metadata file is stored in JSON. The file can be huge. There is an initiative to use parquet instead of JSON.

2.3. TileDB

TileDB (<https://tiledb.com/>) works with multi-dimensional arrays/datasets and is a high-performance database. It is not a data lake, while it has some similarities with Beacon. It seems complex to use when you have millions of datasets with various structures, requiring conversion of native files to tiledb files. It is a commercial product and most probably quite costly.

2.4. ERDDAP and Beacon use case by EMODnet Physics

ERDDAP (<https://github.com/ERDDAP/erddap>) is a scientific data server that gives users a simple, consistent way to download subsets of gridded and tabular scientific datasets in common file formats and make graphs and maps. ERDDAP is a Free and Open Source (Apache and Apache-like) Java Servlet from NOAA NMFS SWFSC Environmental Research Division (ERD). It is well used in the ocean and climate community and it is also successfully promoted by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) for connecting observing networks. As such it is also used and promoted a lot as part of EMODnet Physics to manage its large network of NRT observing data sources and to support operators of operational observing networks to connect their stations for NRT and delayed mode exchanges.

ERDDAP also provides functionality for subsetting. However, considering the large number of data sets and their big volume, partner ETT as coordinator and central operator of EMODnet Physics is looking into

solutions that can support subsetting with high performance and that can work underneath and together with the ERDDAP service for discovery and access. In that framework, EMODnet Physics is successfully exploring the use of the Beacon tool.

EMODnet Physics has a function to extract time series for selected observing stations and then to plot a graph with these time series. ETT compared the following configurations:

Figure 3 – Ingestion through ERDDAP as intermediary between the NetCDF storage and the Graphics engine and presentation window of EMODnet Physics

Figure 4 – Ingestion through Beacon as intermediary between the NetCDF storage and the Graphics engine and presentation window of EMODnet Physics

A total of **2.174.403 NetCDF files**, amounting to **2.5TB** of data, were ingested. The NetCDF files concerned **monthly data** for each platform, totaling approximately **75,000 platforms** (multiple files per platform). The Beacon data lake currently utilises **127GB** of disk space. The importing phase was successfully completed in just **a couple of days**, whereby the ingesting of data is streamlined with the user-friendly **Beacon API**.

Various types of queries were executed to test performance:

Figure 5 – Overview of tests performed for situation with ERDDAP versus situation with Beacon

As a result, Beacon was found to be **10 times faster** than ERDDAP (sometimes even more).

ETT is also happy with the support given for Beacon by MARIS which resulted in overcoming a few identified inefficiencies by means of an upgraded version of Beacon. These are highlighted below.

For each platform EMODnet Physics has **more than one NetCDF file** and in Beacon each NetCDF file is imported as a **single dataset with a unique ID**. See image below.

Figure 6 – Ingesting multiple files per platform

Previously, **to filter data by platform** it was necessary to save in a local DB a relation between platform and Beacon dataset ID. However, the latest Beacon now offers the ability **to filter using dataset attributes** (e.g., file global metadata). This enhancement has eliminated the need for manual dataset ID associations.

NetCDF are stored with a monthly aggregation and are updated one or more times a day. Previously, each time a NetCDF file is updated, it was necessary to perform manual removal of a corresponding dataset and import the updated file, while maintaining in a local DB the relation between NetCDF file (with modification timestamp) and Beacon dataset ID for deletion and recreation of datasets. While, the latest Beacon now offers folder monitoring, which continuously monitors NetCDF file directories and automatically removes and re-imports datasets upon file updates. This streamlined process eliminates manual steps.

The conclusions of ETT as an operator of EMODnet Physics are:

- Beacon is very efficient in returning the subsets of requested data and will be adopted in the operational workflow of EMODnet Physics
- EMODnet Physics will continue to use ERDDAP as a standard tool for the data and metadata flow from observing networks to the EMODnet Physics data storage
- Considering these experiences, Beacon is a promising tool in the pipeline management chain of the Blue-Cloud 2026 workbenches, as it will allow it to extract and harmonise large data sets as required by the Workbenches.

2.5. Conclusion on way forward

After consideration and positive tests on some BDI data collections, it was decided at the latest STC meeting, 5-6 March 2024 to embrace the **Beacon** technology for deploying data lakes for Blue-Cloud 2026, both for VRE users as well as for arranging data provision for WorkBenches. This applies in particular for WorkBench 1 (T&S) and Workbench 2 (Eutrophication), while WorkBench 3 will continue to solve its data provision itself, also because subsetting of biodiversity and biogenomics data are more text search driven, while Beacon excels in processing numerical data.

Considering the potential of the Beacon software and the great interest during demonstrations, not only in the Blue-Cloud community, but also wider such as e.g. the EuroGOOS operational oceanography community, MARIS in the meantime had accelerated its development. Thereby, the Beacon development is challenged by the WorkBench requirements which are seeking homogeneous output from multiple data repositories and data collections, not only for parameters and units, but also for a core set of metadata, involving semantic mappings (where possible). For that purpose, there is a relation with the activities that are progressing for Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 concerning the establishment of semantic expressions and interoperability between the output of several BDIs as federated in the Data Discovery & Access Service. Further developments for the data lakes will be done in close cooperation between MARIS, NOC-BODC, CNR, selected BDIs, and the teams of WorkBenches 1 and 2, in particular for solving the metadata and vocabularies mapping challenges.

3. Planned configurations

As a result of the discussions between WP2 and WP3 WorkBench teams and the overall discussions at the recent STC meeting, 5-6 March 2024, in Amsterdam - Netherlands, two main use cases have been formulated.

- A number of Beacon instances, each for selected data from a specific BDI, and made available for all Blue-Cloud VRE users;
- Two Beacon instances for WorkBench 1 respectively WorkBench 2, merging and harmonising selected data from multiple BDIs, and with regular and controlled updating mechanism, in connection with the DD&AS, and made available to the 2 WorkBenches.

In a later stadium, a third use case will be considered, making use of data lakes for bridging Blue-Cloud federated data output from BDIs and from the WorkBenches with the Digital Twins of the Oceans (DTO), in particular with its European EDITO (EDITO-Infra and EDITO-Modellab) infrastructures. This is the subject of Task 2.4 - DTO Taskforce for tuning Blue-Cloud data lakes with DTO developments. Conceptually, this task is well underway, following a meeting of the Taskforce, held in February 2024, in Toulouse - France. More about Task 2.4 will be available in Deliverable **D2.6 - Tuning between Blue-Cloud Data Lakes and DTO development, 1st report.**

3.1. Blue-Cloud landscape of Beacon instances for selected BDIs and data collections

One plan is to provide subsetting services on selected BDIs to VRE users for use in their Vlab developments and operations. For this purpose, it is planned to configure a number of Beacon instances at the Blue-Cloud VRE (D4Science e-infrastructure). The deployment will be done using Docker containers for the software and Docker volumes for the data contents. It will be possible to update Docker volumes by replacing these, which is a manual activity, but in a later stage, a dynamic and automatic solution will be formulated and elaborated.

In this stage, the choice of Beacon instances is prioritised by the data requirements of WorkBenches 1 and 2. Their teams have indicated the following data requirements:

WorkBench 1: Temperature & Salinity with ultimate focus on global but initially for Mediterranean region:

- CMEMS – CORA data collections
- World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths
- Euro-Argo - Argo

- SeaDataNet T&S Collection V2 data collection (1950-2019)

Three of these data sets are fixed data products that are updated on specific cycles of many months to years. Moreover, these data products all have metadata about the data integrated into the data files. While the fourth data set is a collection of EuroArgo - Argo profiles, frozen in time (up to November 2023), the EuroArgo - Argo service regularly receives additional data sets and possible updates of existing data sets. Therefore, in a later stage, a dynamic maintenance arrangement will have to be established to stay up-to-date. Furthermore, the EuroArgo - Argo fleet monitoring dashboard contains metadata that is not integrated into the actual NetCDF data sets, while the WorkBench teams would like to see both the data and metadata merged in Beacon. This also requires additional functionality from Beacon which will be developed.

WorkBench 2: Eutrophication with focus only on North East Atlantic Ocean region:

- EMODnet Chemistry Eutrophication collection – North East Atlantic
- World Ocean Database (WOD) actual depths (see earlier)
- CMEMS BGC data collections

All three data sets are fixed data products that are updated on specific cycles (multiple months to years). Moreover, these data products all have metadata about the data integrated in the data files.

Next to these Beacon instances, other instances might be foreseen or requested by the VRE users and/or BDIs, which will be considered and gradually taken into production. For instance, there are already Beacon prototypes for SeaDataNet CDI (all unrestricted NetCDF files) and ERA5, which could be promoted to the production level.

The following image gives a Blue-Cloud VRE landscape with monolithic Beacon instances. Monolithic means in this case that each Beacon instance is set up for one BDI source, which guarantees internal integrity and homogeneity.

Figure 7 – Blue-Cloud VRE Landscape of Beacon instances for selected BDIs / data collections

As part of the deployment at the Blue-Cloud VRE, all Beacon instances will be integrated with the **D4Science federated AAI service**, by which access will be arranged. This is instrumental for users routing Beacon extracted data sets towards their personal storage at the Blue-Cloud VRE, which will be done by a push mechanism, already available in D4Science, from Beacon to Blue-Cloud personal storage. Also, it will contribute to maintaining an administration or aggregated log by a service at MARIS to gather KPIs on the usage of the Beacon instances. This will be done by registering queries, numbers of transactions and data output, divided over original data providers, and identities of users at organisation and country level derived from the federated AAI (no personal information to respect GDPR policy of D4Science). The KPIs will be shared through the service at MARIS with managers of BDIs for their specific data sets, so that they are informed about the use of their data sets and have justification for their management.

The following image gives an architecture as planned for deploying a Beacon instance at the D4Science e-infrastructure.

Figure 8 – Architecture overview of Beacon deployment at D4Science e-infrastructure including D4Science federated AAI and MARIS Administration service

3.2. Integrated Beacon instances for supporting Blue-Cloud Work Benches

The second plan is to develop the data provision service for the WorkBenches 1 and 2 by configuring two integrated Beacon instances, one dedicated for each WorkBench, by merging the data set collections as mentioned above under 3.1. These two integrated Beacon instances will also be made available at the Blue-Cloud VRE (D4Science e-infrastructure), but only for the WorkBench teams, so that they can perform their activities in a regulated way. This will be explained later in more detail.

The challenge for the integrated Beacon instances will be to bring, where possible, parameters, units, quality flags, and associated core metadata from the individual data collections under a homogeneous index.

The planned workflow for the WorkBenches is illustrated in the following images from WorkBench 1 (T&S) and is in principle comparable with the planned workflow of WorkBench 2 (eutrophication), although their required data sources are somewhat different.

Figure 9 – Planned workflow for WorkBench 1

Figure 10 – Planned workflow for WorkBench 1 with webODV as tool for quality control and duplicates detection

Mapping analyses needed for homogenisation of Beacon output:

This will require for each WorkBench a focus on those parameters that are relevant for the specific WorkBench EOVs, and striving for harmonisation of individual parameters by using their mapping to the SeaDataNet P35 aggregated parameter vocabulary: <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P35/current/>. Or else to the A05 Atlantos Essential Aggregated Variables: <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/A05/current>

P35 defines numerous aggregated variables by specifying the list of contributing SeaDataNet P01 variables as well as the preferred units. See for instance how multiple terms from the P01 parameters usage vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/>) are mapped to one P35 term for 'ITS-90 WATER TEMPERATURE': <http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P35/current/WATERTEMP/>. While A05 has been developed to align with P01, as used by SeaDataNet, as well as P35 used by EMODnet Chemistry, and R03 utilized by EuroArgo-Argo, along with various other BDIs for aggregated parameters. These relations can be retrieved by Beacon making use of the iADOPT Framework Ontology (<https://i-adopt.github.io/index.html>) which is maintained by NOC-BODC as part of the NERC Vocabulary Service (NVS). Any necessary unit conversion rules can be retrieved and applied using factors and offsets as already listed in https://odv.awi.de/fileadmin/user_upload/odv/sdn_unit_conversions.txt. However, additional mappings might be needed from other vocabularies in use to the SeaDataNet target vocabularies.

Harmonisation is not only planned for parameters and units, but also for a core set of metadata, that have been selected by the WorkBench teams from the indicated data set collections as necessary for harmonisation and following actions. Beacon will be used to integrate the different BDI data set collections and to facilitate the WorkBench teams to prepare subsets and export these in a homogeneous way (concerning parameters, units, quality flags, and core metadata) which then are loaded into the webODV online service, to be deployed also at the Blue-Cloud VRE, for the analytical steps. Steps in webODV will include activities such as checking and identification of duplicates and Quality Analysis and Quality Control activities. For this, a new version of webODV is being developed as part of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project by AWI, namely a read-and-write version which will feature many functionalities for analyses, plots, annotations, and exports. The final export of the WorkBenches will be highly qualified, validated, and harmonised data set collections for selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs).

For Beacon it is necessary to learn the required fields, mappings and unit conversions which will be formulated as filters in Beacon for efficient conversion from heterogeneous input to homogeneous output. For the formulation of the mappings, MARIS as Beacon developer and operator will rely on the WorkBench teams that are far more knowledgeable about the different data collections and their scientific contents and that already are underway with their mapping analyses. They are supported in this effort by NOC-BODC which has established and is operating the NERC Vocabulary Service and has a

dedicated expertise in semantics and ontologies. NOC-BODC has developed and is maintaining a **Semantic Analyser** (<https://semantics.bodc.ac.uk/>), which is a tool to analyse the semantic elements of metadata and data files from a wide range of data resources across multiple domains (atmospheric, marine, terrestrial). The SA is capable of extracting semantic content from metadata and data files encoded in various formats. In its first version, it supports netCDF data file formats and XML ISO 19115 harmonised metadata records coming from the DAB service. Upon completion of the analysis, the SA provides a list of terms that have been successfully extracted, along with information about the matched semantic artefacts. Analyses are performed against the Semantic Analyser Knowledge Base which already contains many terms from multiple BDIs and associate mappings. This will speed up the mapping. This concerns not only parameters and units but also many elements from the core metadata profile that might be supported by other SeaDataNet vocabularies such as platforms (L06 (types) and C17 (instances)), instruments (L05 (types) and L22 (models)), cruises (CSR), projects (EDMERP), organisations (EDMO), and others. The further development of the Semantic Analyser is shared with the EU FAIR-EASE project which serves as a development space for the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

CNR and MARIS will contribute to this mapping and harmonisation efforts which should lead to the information needed for setting the filters in the integrated Beacon instances. As a parallel activity, there is also upgrading of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS) ongoing. See Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2. Among others, this involves including semantic expressions in the core metadata for the BDIs that are federated for the DD&AS and seeking semantic interoperability for terms as used by BDIs in core metadata fields. For this purpose, CNR has already made online reports per BDI of the terms as used per core metadata field, which NOC-BODC is taking on board of their analyses.

Furthermore, as part of the Beacon single instances, see Section 3.1 above, Beacon can be used to extract “footprints” per data set collection of the metadata fields in use and their content ranges. Thereby, Beacon could make these extracts of content ranges per metadata field per BDI, focusing on parameters and units, and core metadata fields as selected by the WorkBench teams, while treating other remaining metadata fields and their contents as secondary metadata, for which no harmonisation is possible and necessary.

Both CNR and MARIS will share their “footprint” findings with NOC-BODC and WorkBench teams as this will contribute to establishing, where possible, mappings, which then will lead to instructions for Beacon on which filters to include as part of the indexing.

Figure 11 – Architecture of the Semantic Analyser (SA) of NOC-BODC

The Semantic Analyser (SA) knowledge base is composed of a number of ontologies and vocabularies. These form a set of reference data against which metadata or data elements can be matched. The ontologies and vocabularies have been organised into named graphs, with the named graph URIs typically being the namespace of the vocabulary or ontology, which allows easier organisation, searching, and updating. The ontologies and vocabularies have been categorised into the metadata elements (Keywords, Instruments, Parameters, and Platforms) that the terms within the vocabulary describe. To enhance the matching results and expand the scope of the Knowledge Base, the Search Algorithm can also reach out to external terminology repositories in a federated search approach in order to find controlled vocabularies for terms that were present in the metadata file but not found in the SA Knowledge Base. This first version of the SA uses the APIs of two terminology repositories that could have relevant [BioPortal](#) and [EarthPortal](#). This functionality provides valuable insights into the semantic conventions employed by data providers and also helps identify additional terminology of interest. The newly discovered sources can then become a candidate for inclusion into the Knowledge Base.

Connecting WorkBench Beacons to DD&AS for updating of specific source data sets:

As indicated earlier, not all of the selected data set collections are fixed products, but are dynamic with new incoming data sets and updates of existing data sets. For the BDIs selected as priority for the two WorkBenches this will be the case for EuroArgo-Argo and for SeaDataNet CDI data discovery and access service. Moreover, for both BDIs, it will be needed to merge into Beacon both the NetCDF data files and the extended metadata files from their discovery services. In the case of SeaDataNet, it concerns supplementing the CDI - data entries that were earlier used in the SeaDataCloud project to generate the

SeaDataNet T&S Collection V2 data collection (1950-2019). The supplement will aim at all new and updated T&S data sets populated after July 2019. The Beacon functionality will be expanded for retrieving selected metadata and data sets from dynamic BDIs and loading and merging these into the Beacon instances, both for the mono versions (see §3.1) and the integrated WorkBenches. To do so, a linkage is proposed between the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service and the Beacon instances.

Dashboard for regulating and administering harvests:

The WorkBenches, once in production, will work with production cycles. For instance, each 6 or 12 months, an updated version of an EOVS data collection could be generated, adding the new and updated data from the last period to the existing and already validated EOVS data collection product. This implies that the WorkBench teams would prefer to keep control of the new harvests of the BDIs using the DD&AS and control of the new and updated ingestions. That way, they can focus on only the incremental metadata and data sets, while not having to process again the data sets that were already validated in the previous run. MARIS will develop a dashboard for use by WorkBench operators which will keep track of the latest harvests from BDIs and track of latest ingestions.

Figure 12 – Blue-Cloud Integrated Beacon instances with dashboard and connectivity to DD&AS and webODV for supporting the WorkBench teams with regulated and harmonised metadata and data provision for EOVS generation

Export from Beacon to webODV:

The current output of Beacon is a NetCDF file, but for import into webODV, an output format based upon the ODV ASCII format is requested by AWI, the developer and manager of webODV. This Beacon ODV output format should include the metadata and the data. Therefore, an alternative output driver is being developed by MARIS together with AWI.

To be able to produce an ODV, Beacon has to split its single harmonised response format into various categories such as, profiles, time series and trajectories. This splitting is required as Beacon harmonises everything to a single output format (eg. profiles, time series and trajectories are all stored/represented in the same manner) while ODV requires them to be split into separate categories. To perform this splitting, AWI has created a script that recognizes the differences between profiles, time series and trajectories. This script will split the ODV file that Beacon creates into separate ODV files. This script is available at: https://github.com/smieruch/beacon_odv_exporter. At the same time MARIS has created a Beacon ODV output driver that can generate the input for AWI's script that splits these ODV files which Beacon repackages as a single ZIP file.

Already it has been possible to visualise (in webODV) a query response from a test instance of Beacon containing a small collection of datasets. This will be tested more thoroughly on the entire open

SeaDataNet CDI Collection. With AWI a Beacon endpoint is shared that can be used to query a Beacon development instance. This way MARIS and AWI can develop on both sides of the script (Input for the script and output of the script). Furthermore, MARIS is testing a new version of Beacon on the entire SeaDataNet CDI collection including metadata merging to run various queries to test the correctness of the ODV output driver by visualising every response in webODV.

4. Conclusions and follow-up

In the previous chapter the two main configurations are described that are planned and being under development for equipping the Blue-Cloud infrastructure with subsetting capabilities on the data and metadata as managed by selected Blue Data Infrastructures, not only from Europe, but also internationally. The implementation will be done by adopting the Beacon technology as developed and managed by MARIS and adapting this technology to deploy and configure data lakes in two configurations to support on one hand Blue-Cloud VRE users for their analytics and VLab developments and operations, and on the other side to support two of the Blue-Cloud WorkBenches (no 1 and 2) for their data and metadata provision as an integrated component of the foreseen WorkBench workflows:

- A number of Beacon instances, each for selected data from a specific BDI, and made available for all Blue-Cloud VRE users;
- Two Beacon instances for WorkBench 1 respectively WorkBench 2, merging and harmonising selected data from multiple BDIs, and with regular and controlled updating mechanism, in connection with the DD&AS, and made available to the 2 WorkBenches.

The implementation of both configurations is underway and also is done interacting with the developments for Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 for optimising and expanding the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service (DD&AS).

The implementation is planned in three stages, namely aiming for delivery of:

- working monolithic Beacon instances by end June 2024
- working integrated Beacon instances, interoperable with webODV, for use by the WorkBenches 1 and 2 by end August 2024
- dynamic harvesting and ingestion functionality and dashboard for regulated use of the whole data provision pipeline by the WorkBenches 1 and 2 by end 2024 in sync with delivery of the optimised DD&AS

Achieving these milestones will require a lot of development activity from the major stakeholders, which are MARIS, CNR, NOC-BODC, and WorkBench 1 and 2 teams, while in specific cases also managers of BDIs will be consulted. The greatest challenge will be establishing mapping for harmonisation of the parameters, units, quality flags, and core metadata between the different BDI metadata and data sets that are needed for the further WorkBench analyses. Luckily, there is already a lot of previous experience in this domain and there are controlled vocabularies, ontologies, and semantic tools available for progressing this challenge. For sure, it will not be possible to achieve a full harmonisation, but a workable solution for a common denominator should be feasible, in particular when focusing on those parameters, which are key for the targeted EOVs.

The coming deliverables are planned as follows:

- **D2.3: Optimised and expanded Blue Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service – Documentation Report:** Report documenting the new release of the Blue Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service with optimised services, semantic interoperability, new BDIs connected, and new or adapted discovery and access BDI web services (**M24 (end 2024) – MARIS**),
- **D2.5: Established BDI sub-setting APIs and Data Lakes – Documentation Report:** Report documenting the release of the Blue Cloud Data Lakes, their architecture and deployment, and the established sub-setting APIs at each BDI (**M26 (end Feb 2025) – MARIS**),
- **D2.7: Tuning between Blue-Cloud Data Lakes and DTO development, 2nd report:** Progress report about the tuning process and the interfacing between the Blue-Cloud Data Lakes development and the DTO development (**M26 (end Feb 2025)– MOI**).